

Digital transcript counting by Xist and the ICR gene products Ftx, Jpx and Tsix.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

East Islip, NY USA 11730

We demonstrate here that Xist and genes encoded at the X inactivation center (XIC) are maintained at a defined quantity in the human cell. We present a model for “digital” counting of transcripts within the cell by Xist XIC gene products Tsix, Ftx and Jpx, which functioned to maintain transcriptional homeostasis at the single cell level. Xist and each of the XIC gene products were present in the cell in defined ratio, and this defined ratio is the basis by which a strict stoichiometric ratio of a non-coding RNA with gene regulatory properties provides a basic schema by which counting of mRNA transcripts for to maintain precise gene expression limits could occur.

Xist 50 (equivalent to 5000 mRNAs)

Tsix 25 (20-25) (equivalent to 2000-2500 mRNAs)

Jpx 0.5 (equivalent to 0.5 mRNA)

Ftx 1. (equivalent to 1 mRNA)

While Xist XIC gene products were broadly maintained cross tissue- and cell-type, alterations of this composition were also observed. Changes in Xist XIC gene product ratio and complex composition were highly suggestive of a cellular event that induced Xist activation resulting from threshold transgression from external stimuli but reminiscent of processes which likely occur during embryonic and adult organ and tissue development involving Xist coordination of cell-type specification and development. The data alluded to a general mechanism by which Xist or an associated gene product, like a sequence-specific homeobox, could bind transcripts of the genome for Xist non-coding RNA regulatory control across activation context.

Citations

1. Sunwoo, H., Wu, J.Y. and Lee, J.T., 2015. The Xist RNA-PRC2 complex at 20-nm resolution reveals a low Xist stoichiometry and suggests a hit-and-run mechanism in mouse cells. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(31), pp.E4216-E4225.

2. Markaki, Y., Chong, J.G., Wang, Y., Jacobson, E.C., Luong, C., Tan, S.Y., Jachowicz, J.W., Strehle, M., Maestrini, D., Banerjee, A.K. and Mistry, B.A., 2021. Xist nucleates local protein gradients to propagate silencing across the X chromosome. *Cell*, 184(25), pp.6174-6192.

3. Battich, N., Stoeger, T. and Pelkmans, L., 2015. Control of transcript variability in single mammalian cells. *Cell*, 163(7), pp.1596-1610.